

ARCSS Program | Message from the ARCSS Committee

ARCSS Note #6 (20 September 2005): ARCSS Synthesis eTown Meeting

The ARCSS Committee is sponsoring an eTown Meeting on ARCSS synthesis that will focus on the results of the recent NSF **Announcement of Opportunity** (<http://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2005/nsf05525/nsf05525.htm>) and near-term planning for system-wide research and synthesis. This is the third eTown meeting in a series on ARCSS synthesis and re-organization.

The eTown Meeting is scheduled for Friday, 7 October 2005 at 10:00 a.m. Alaska Daylight Time (11:00 a.m. PDT; 12:00 p.m. MDT; 1:00 p.m. CDT; 2:00 p.m. EDT). Advance registration is *required*.

We recognize that because of schedule conflicts, not everyone who wishes to participate in this eTown Meeting will be able to do so. A **comment form** ([survey_etown.html](#)) will be available soon for contributing questions or specific issues you feel are important. This submission form ([survey_etown.html](#)) will be announced via the ARCSS Listserve and will be available before, during, and after the online meeting so that anyone may participate in the process regardless of participation in the eTown Meeting. The eTown Meeting will be archived and available for viewing after the actual online session.

The NSF ARCSS Program is interested in broad community input to ARCSS planning. Community discussions during this eTown Meeting and through the online comment process will provide an opportunity for individuals and groups to comment on recent and future ARCSS Synthesis announcements of opportunity and to discuss other potential synthesis activities.

Previous ARCSS eTown meetings have been invaluable as a forum for community discussions on various aspects of ARCSS Program planning; the ARCSS Committee hopes you will join this upcoming online meeting to help guide future synthesis efforts.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

The eTown Meeting platform is HorizonWimba; this platform enables online presentations and real-time interaction. To participate in the web portion of the conference, you will need access to an Internet connection in addition to your phone line; participants also have the option to participate via phone only. Web-platform login and call-in instructions will be sent to all registered participants in advance.

Please prepare for the eTown meeting by running the HorizonWimba wizard (on the computer that you intend to use when you participate) to make sure that your computer is properly configured. To access the wizard, go to <http://channel.horizonwimba.com> (<http://channel.horizonwimba.com>) and click on "run the Setup Wizard." Computer microphones will not be used for the October eTown Meeting, as all the audio will be over traditional teleconference lines.

PLEASE NOTE

Due to recent upgrades to the HorizonWimba platform, you must run the wizard even if you have run it successfully in the past.

Registration Deadline: Tuesday, 4 October 2005

For more information, visit the **[eTown Meeting webpage \(ETM/October_05/index.html\)](#)**.

ARCSS Committee:

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